

Annex 3: Identifiable barriers and enablers for replication schemes

Table 1 Barriers and enablers for replication schemes

Category	Key barriers	Key enablers
Governance & policy	<p>Policy/regulatory gaps: absence of coherent SWM legislation and enforcement at the appropriate administrative level, underdeveloped sector-specific regulation for environmental impacts of bio-based production and novel waste-to-product systems, unclear authorisation and legitimisation of entities introducing circular/bio-based technologies into supply chains, limited certification and approval pathways for innovative bio-based products and technologies.</p> <p>Weak monitoring and data systems: lack of standardised measurement and reporting, fragmented institutional responsibilities, donor-driven monitoring systems that are rarely integrated into national systems, high reliance on informal or unrecorded actors, complicating baselines and performance evaluation.</p>	<p>EU-level political commitment and sector-wide frameworks: EU interest in climate-proofed humanitarian aid and the “do no harm the environment” principle, the Climate and Environment Charter for Humanitarian Organizations signalling sector expectations, increasing donor attention to environmental sustainability in humanitarian operations.</p> <p>Strategic SWM governance reforms: developing national/regional SWM regulations coupled with enforcement, promotion, and public operational plans, adopting decentralised SWM approaches where appropriate, involving private-sector actors in plan design.</p> <p>Humanitarian organisational policy shifts already underway: examples of internal policy and logistics guideline updates, waste tracking and baseline systems, staff trainings and</p>

		<p>awareness programmes, and operationalisation of minimum environmental standards within participating organisations.</p> <p>Multi-stakeholder coordination mechanisms: platforms and projects that connect governments, humanitarian actors, donors, private waste enterprises, bio-based solution providers and academia, structured stakeholder databases and standardised assessment tools to align actions across locations (urban, rural, camp).</p>
Financing	<p>Financing constraints: limited public resources, insufficient or narrowly scoped donor funding for operational greening and end-of-life management, investment uncertainty for durable infrastructure in protracted crises.</p>	<p>Financing models that blend public, private and donor capital: PPPs and fee-based systems, fiscal incentives (e.g. temporary tax reductions) to grow local waste-management enterprises, structured outreach to international donors and development banks for infrastructure and service upgrades.</p>
Infrastructure & services	<p>Infrastructure and enabling services deficits: limited treatment and disposal options tailored to distinct waste streams, limited electricity access and</p>	<p>Locally led circular ventures and enterprise partnerships: engaging local waste collectors and transformers to</p>

	<p>underdeveloped road networks, shortages of technical expertise, security constraints that limit service coverage and investments, limited segregation and collection systems for organic and biodegradable waste streams.</p> <p>End-of-life (EoL) risks and contamination: biodegradable/compostable products often require specific conditions and/or industrial facilities, biodegradable plastics may require separate collection and can contaminate recyclable plastics, landfill breakdown can generate methane emissions if mismanaged, limited community awareness of correct disposal requirements.</p>	<p>create circular linkages (collection, transformation, reuse), and enabling safer access to waste streams to allow SMEs and community actors to participate.</p>
<p>Procurement & markets</p>	<p>Procurement and supply-chain frictions: additional resources, staff capacity, and time required to implement green procurement and end-of-life programmes, uncertain demand for bio-based alternatives in humanitarian supply chains, difficulty mainstreaming sustainability criteria across all supply-chain stages (including intermediate repacking and reloading phases).</p> <p>Market and cost barriers for bio-based options: higher unit costs for many bio-based alternatives (examples cited: paper bags ~1.7× and jute bags ~3.5–4× more expensive than plastic), feedstock cost and availability constraints (feedstock can represent 60–70% of production cost), especially for scaling volumes required by humanitarian actors.</p>	<p>Green procurement rules and tender criteria: structured procurement steps that embed environmental criteria across the procurement cycle, packaging sustainability criteria (reduced virgin plastic, recyclable cardboard, systematic consideration of non-plastic alternatives) opening a pathway to bio-based packaging substitution, inclusion of life-cycle considerations in procurement decisions.</p>

<p>Knowledge & capacity</p>	<p>Low awareness and acceptance: limited familiarity with “bioeconomy” and “bio-based solutions” among local stakeholders, concerns about slow/complicated/costly implementation, limited institutional capacity to assess, communicate, and monitor benefits and risks.</p>	<p>Guidance, tools and capacity-building resources: UNEP and WREC methodologies supporting waste characterisation and measurement, adoption of organisational tools like NEAT+ for project screening, training on LCA/LCC to build evidence-based decision-making, Training-of-Trainers approaches and demonstration sites.</p>
<p>Environmental & social factors</p>	<p>Environmental and social trade-offs: potential competition between bio-feedstock cultivation and food production, risks from overharvesting/large-scale farming of certain feedstocks (seaweed), potential for higher impacts in certain LCA categories if solutions are poorly matched to local conditions.</p>	<p>Evidence generation through LCA/LCC and feasibility work: planned economic (LCC) and environmental (LCA) assessments to support credible claims, reduce perceived risk, and inform regulatory recognition and donor buy-in.</p> <p>Community engagement and social acceptance: early stakeholder engagement, trusted community channels, demonstration activities, and locally adapted sensitisation approaches can improve understanding, acceptance, and long-term adoption of bio-based solutions.</p>